

User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration

Authors:

Poppy Townsend ^{1,2} ,
Molly MacRae ^{1,2} ,
David Poulter ^{1,2} ,
Louise Darroch ^{1,6} , Seni Osunkoya ⁷

Affiliations:

- 1 - NERC Environmental Data Service
- 2 - Science and Technology Facilities Council
- 3 - British Geological Survey
- 4 - British Antarctic Survey
- 5 - UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology
- 6 - National Oceanography Centre
- 7 - Digital Solutions Hub, University of Manchester

Executive Summary

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. This report provides a summary of the user centred work, including; why this work is important, what we did, and what are the next steps.

To create tailored tools and data services that improve our ability to mitigate and respond to environmental challenges, we need to understand how to efficiently communicate complex information to the intended audience. User centred approaches can be used to:

- Improve data services: tailor tools and services to better meet the needs of diverse users
- Enhance communication: efficiently convey complex environmental data to varied audiences
- Support open science: encourage collaboration and improve data accessibility across disciplines

Four challenges were identified for implementing user centred approaches across the EDS; 1. Ineffective sharing of learnings, 2. Engagement with peers and conflicting priorities, 3. Lack of time/resources, 4. Difficulty engaging with users/stakeholders. A diverse portfolio of work was designed with these challenges in mind.

The project identified three key areas for improvement, with recommendations for future work:

1. People and communities: we must foster a collaborative environment and build a network for sharing challenges and successes.
 - a. Establish an international network of experts in environmental data and user centred approaches
 - b. Set up a consultant group within EDS for user centred approaches
 - c. Organise networking opportunities for people interested in user centred approaches
2. Processes, governance, and strategy: we must operationalise findings, embed user centred approaches in strategy, and explore creative methods for undertaking new work in difficult financial landscapes
 - a. Outsource work in creative ways, such as pitching projects to MSc students
 - b. Pilot using holacracy software to define and visualise the diverse roles and expertise of staff across the EDS
 - c. Embed in strategy to ensure long-term integration of user centred approaches
 - d. Funders to promote trusted experts as collaborators
3. Information management: ensure unrestricted access to project documents and resources to promote transparent collaborations and reduce duplication
 - a. Operationalise the toolkit into a fully supported EDS service
 - b. Disseminate findings with priority stakeholders

This project has laid the groundwork for embedding user centred approaches in environmental data services, enhancing user experience and fostering collaboration. In order to continue to embed and mature user centred approaches, the EDS need consistent research and design methods, a culture of knowledge sharing, measurable outcomes and strong leadership. The recommendations aim to ensure these approaches are integrated into future projects and strategies, promoting a user centred culture within the EDS and beyond.

Contents

About the report	5
Why did we do this?	7
What do we know now?	10
Summary	10
Detailed synthesis	13
What next?	24
Conclusion	29
Supporting materials	30

About the report

We believe this report will be useful to anyone who designs, develops and maintains data services for environmental science - and research data services more broadly.

About the Environmental Data Service

The [Environmental Data Service](#) (EDS) provides a focal point for scientific data and information spanning all environmental science domains: atmosphere and climate, earth observation, polar and cryosphere, marine, terrestrial and freshwater, geoscience, solar and space physics. The EDS is made up of a network of distributed data centres, with domain specific expertise.

Our main goal is to ensure that environmental data are made available, accessible and re-usable for the long-term in order to fully realise their value. We are funded by the [Natural Environment Research Council \(NERC\)](#), part of [UK Research and Innovation](#), to advise researchers on how to prepare data for long term storage and dissemination.

The EDS is a fundamental part of [NERC's digital strategy](#) and works with the [Digital Solutions Hub](#), and other partners, to break down disciplinary barriers and facilitate data sharing beyond academic use.

About the project

The BOOST EDS project, one of [four pilot projects, funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aims to improve how researchers use and access data. The project, undertaken between late 2023 to March 2025, was split into five work packages:

WP1 - developing a new service to develop persistent identifiers to create Digital Object Identifiers for sensors. Researchers will be able to register their sensors, what they do, the parameters, latest calibration, how they relate to other sensors, and so on. This will enable better traceability of data from related sensors and support integrated data workflows.

WP2 - pilot the integration of sensitive data (e.g. public health or socio-economic) with relevant environmental data sets of TByte scale and larger (e.g. climate scenarios) via a federated Trusted Research Environment.

WP3 - building modular workflows so that they can reuse elements of the workflows in other activities. Elements, such as recording provenance and complex citations, will link with WP1.

WP4 - assessing interoperability of data analysis platforms, with the aim of developing best practice on Jupyter notebooks, and will include recommendations for future cross domain opportunities.

WP5 - exploring co-creation and user centred approaches for data services and how to share good practices across the EDS and beyond. Ensuring our services are fit for purpose is becoming more important as a broader range of people find and access our data.

This report aims to summarise the work undertaken in WP5 by:

- Providing examples that we have piloted to help address challenges for implementing user centred approaches in an environmental data service context
- Identifying opportunities and recommendations for future work, both within environmental data services and more broadly, to support open science, encourage collaboration and improve data accessibility for cross-disciplinary users

Why did we do this?

To create tailored tools and data services that improve our ability to mitigate and respond to environmental challenges, we need to understand how to efficiently communicate complex information to the intended audience.

This has become particularly critical in recent years, where the user base of environmental data has continuously expanded, with more variations between the knowledge and experience of users, and hence their expectations, means of accessing data, and needs. As environmental data is increasingly embedded in a wide spectrum of sectors and fields, environmental scientists and organisations directly investigating the natural world are no longer our only target audience. Today, sectors such as healthcare, economy, education and governance are using environmental data as primary inputs into their essential workflows, which reflects on the increasing impact of environmental data across all aspects of society. Accordingly, our role as government-funded custodians of the UK's environmental research data needs to evolve: we must adapt to cater for the needs of these new and growing audiences.

This work directly tackles this gap, focusing on user centred approaches to efficiently convey environmental data use to multiple segments of society with a variety of skill sets, knowledge bases and preferences in accessing data. We want to embed user centred approaches to ensure access to environmental data is equitable and fit for purpose to anyone who needs it.

As the climate and nature emergencies become more imperative to societal workflows, the significance of this work will only increase further. We must be ready to accommodate this increased usage and provide solutions for users with differing needs.

What is user centred design?

user centred design is an iterative approach to designing products and services that prioritises the needs, preferences, and experiences of end-users throughout the development process.

In the context of data services, user centred design ensures that tools, dashboards, and systems are intuitive, accessible, and tailored to the specific tasks and workflows of their users. This approach involves actively engaging with stakeholders through research, testing, and feedback to create solutions that are both functional and user-friendly.

There is varied terminology that is used by those working within the user centred design domain including, but not limited to; user experience, user research, user interface design, user acceptance testing, co-creation, co-design. These terminologies are used in slightly different ways by different domains. To avoid confusion, for this report we will use the broader term 'user centred approaches' to encompass all types of work in this area.

Benefits of user centred approaches

User centred approaches can be used to:

- Improve data services: tailor tools and services to better meet the needs of diverse users
- Enhance communication: efficiently convey complex environmental data to varied audiences
- Support open science: encourage collaboration and improve data accessibility across disciplines

The benefits of user centred approaches include improved user satisfaction, higher adoption rates, and increased efficiency in decision-making, as users can interact seamlessly with the data they need. User centred approaches minimise the risk of developing features that are underutilised or misaligned with user goals, resulting in better resource allocation and greater overall value for organisations.

User centred approaches in the EDS

The EDS is a UK-based initiative funded by the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) to manage, preserve, and provide access to environmental data collected through NERC-funded research and projects. It acts as an overarching umbrella term for five data centres that specialise in different areas of environmental science, such as atmospheric science, marine science, earth observation, biodiversity, and geoscience. Teams are distributed across many UK locations.

The EDS plays a critical role in ensuring that valuable environmental data is accessible to researchers, policymakers, and other stakeholders for use in scientific analysis, policy development, and decision-making. It also promotes data sharing and reuse, which supports open science and helps advance research in areas like climate change, ecosystem health, and natural hazards. Key goals of the EDS include long-term data preservation, compliance with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles, and the facilitation of interdisciplinary research by making data from different domains accessible through a unified framework.

One of the core aims of the EDS is to better engage with users and ensure their needs are central to everything we do. How we design, develop, maintain and share our data services hasn't traditionally been prioritised with user feedback in mind. Many of our teams and systems are now having to change the way we work and learn new skills.

The [Nielsen Norman Group](#), a globally trusted team of user experience experts, state there are [six levels of maturity stages](#) for embedding user centred approaches within organisations (Figure 1).

The EDS's maturity stage is varied across individual teams. To advance maturity of user centred approaches towards level six, the EDS need consistent research and design methods, a culture of knowledge sharing, measurable outcomes and strong leadership.

The BOOST EDS project wanted to tackle this head on, by identifying existing knowledge and challenges, gathering and sharing good practice, and building a network of experts. At the beginning

of the BOOST project, the EDS was at stage two. Following the funding, we are now firmly in stage three.

Figure 1: the six levels of user experience maturity, as defined by the Nielsen Norman Group: <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/ux-maturity-model/>

What do we know now?

Summary

Four key challenges for implementing user centred approaches were identified at the beginning of the project.

1. Ineffective sharing of learnings

We need to share existing information about user centred approaches more effectively and actively encourage learning from each other. There was no central location to share good practice.

2. Engagement with peers and conflicting priorities

Only a handful of individuals have roles which specifically focus on using user centred approaches. Engagement between EDS peers is better than it used to be, but there is still room for improvement. There needs to be clarity about priorities and how our individual missions can contribute to the wider shared vision/goals.

3. Lack of time/resources

There was also no coordination of user centred expertise across our distributed teams (or the environmental data services community more broadly). Staff are juggling lots of different priorities, and may not necessarily be involved directly in this project.

4. Difficult to engage with users/stakeholders

As our data becomes more open, we increasingly struggle to know who is using our data/services. We need to know who the users are, so we can convince them to engage with us.

These challenges were identified during a workshop with 24 experts to discuss barriers to designing and implementing user centred data services ([see detailed workshop findings](#)). Some attendees were more experienced in co-creating services and engaging with users, whereas others understood the importance but historically it hasn't been their focus. It was clear that all attendees believed co-creation and engaging with the intended audience for services was important.

The workshop was used as a collaborative way to identify, shape and prioritise the work for the remainder of the project. Table 1 summarises the challenges, why we want to resolve the issue, how we aimed to do this, the methods used to do the work, and what key themes emerged from the project. A detailed synthesis of each challenge can be found [later in the document](#).

The work undertaken focussed on using collaborative and user centred approaches. Multiple methods were used such as; online meetings, interviews and webinar presentations, creation of new resources (online toolkit, this report, case studies, desk studies), individuals championing and ensuring the topic is embedded in future work and organisational strategies.

Table 1: a summary of challenges, rationales, aims, methods and emerging themes for embedding and enhancing user centred approaches for environmental data services

Challenge	Rationale	Aim	Method/s	Emerging theme/s
Ineffective sharing of learnings	We need to share existing information about co-creation of services more effectively and actively encourage learning from each other.	To share existing information about user centred approaches more effectively	This report, case studies, meetings, webinar, online toolkit, desk study	People and communities Processes, governance and strategy Information management
Engagement with peers and conflicting priorities	Engagement between internal peers is better than it used to be, but there is still room for improvement. There needs to be clarity about priorities and how individual missions can contribute to the wider shared goals.	To improve engagement between peers interested in user centred approaches - both internally (EDS) and more broadly	Interviews with external peers, expert group for internal staff	People and communities Information management
Lack of time/resources	Our staff juggle lots of different priorities, and may not necessarily be involved directly in this project.	To start embedding user centred approaches across the organisation	Champions, 2025-26 roadmap workshop	People and communities Processes, governance and strategy
Difficult to engage with users and stakeholders	As our data becomes more open, we increasingly struggle to know who is using our data/services. We need to know who the users are, so we can convince them to engage with us.	To understand the barriers to engaging with users	Desk study	Processes, governance and strategy

Three key themes for tackling the challenges of developing and implementing user centred approaches for environmental data services were identified:

1. People and communities

To foster a collaborative environment, it's essential to build a network where peers can openly share challenges and successes for their work with user centred data services. A peer-peer network should

provide support, guidance, and information about individuals' skills and expertise, ultimately reducing duplication of effort.

User centred and co-created approaches are applicable across various domains. By leveraging experts in fields outside of our own domain, we can extract specific insights relevant to our own research areas, like environmental science, rather than reiterating general guidance.

A cohesive network of people and communities working with user centred approaches will ensure the data services they are working on are not only functional but also meaningful and responsive to the users they serve.

2. Processes, governance and strategy

To improve existing processes, findings from projects using user centred approaches should be operationalised effectively. Governance structures should ensure that different teams and strategies combine into a shared vision, addressing similar challenges and avoiding siloed working. Embedding user centred approaches into strategy will make them a common practice among staff.

Creative methods, such as pitching user centred projects to MSc students studying user centred approaches, could be explored to achieve this.

3. Information management

Unrestricted access to project documents, staff expertise, contact details, and guidance resources is crucial for effective collaborative working. These resources should be simple, well-organised, and easily accessible to all relevant individuals. This approach encourages collaboration, reduces duplication of effort, and promotes the sharing of work.

Limitations of this work

The work undertaken focussed on environmental, data, or digital expertise and delivery of user centred approaches for data services in these areas. We believe many similarities could be found in other domains, but this work focussed on environmental data services.

It is crucial to emphasise the importance of continuous co-creation and inclusive facilitation, which must be planned and actively considered. These efforts often face time constraints due to funding pressures - which was a significant challenge during this one year project. The limitations of this work include the lack of time to conduct user research and engage directly with users of data services, as well as the limited depth of user centred approaches in some areas.

The team endeavoured to reach out to experts working in related areas across disciplines to share knowledge and inspire new ways of thinking. Whilst the evidence we gathered is extensive, it is by no means complete and should be seen as a starting point.

Detailed synthesis

This section provides a detailed synthesis of the four challenge areas and the associated work undertaken to date. We anticipate readers to skip to specific challenge areas that resonate with your work.

Challenge 1: Ineffective sharing of learnings

There was a clear need to share existing information about co-creation of services more effectively and actively encourage learning from each other. Issues related to this included; a lack of visibility of resources (not sure who to ask or where to look), too much generic information leading to overwhelm, requires a mindset shift within teams. We believe tackling these issues could reduce duplication of effort and improve knowledge sharing across teams.

This is the primary challenge that we tackled. Detailed information about specific work can be found in the evidence section of this report, which is split into three key areas; context setting (Table 2), case studies (Table 3), and knowledge sharing (Table 4).

Context setting

The first area we tackled was to ensure we have a clear evidence-based picture of current practices and issues. A workshop at the beginning of the project was used as a way to collaboratively identify and shape the direction of this work ([see detailed workshop findings](#)). Many actions identified in the workshop have been addressed in the evidence section of this report.

In particular, the current state review, terminology, and policies for contacting our users sections provide a solid foundation for context setting - predominantly within the EDS, but also more widely. A summary of the three areas are below and in Table 2.

1. Interviews: current state review

Purpose: to explore the current state of experience with user centred approaches across the EDS and beyond.

Findings: We interviewed 18 individuals who work in environmental, digital/data or user centred domains specifically. There were many common themes and challenges identified across the interviews.

Outcomes: synthesis of common themes and challenges, list of individuals who are interested in domain specific good practice for user centred approaches. Identified opportunities for future collaborations.

2. Desk study: terminology

Purpose: to provide a better understanding of the jargon used in user centred approaches

Findings: there is lots of jargon, it can be very confusing. Ultimately it doesn't matter what it's called, as long as everyone has a common understanding for each specific use case.

Outcome: decision to use the phrase 'user centred approaches' for this report to avoid confusing use of different terminology.

Table 2: summary of the context setting work

Context setting work			
Title	Purpose	People involved	Further details
Interviews: current state review	To explore the current state of experience with user centred approaches across the EDS and beyond.	Molly MacRae Poppy Townsend Thomas Zwagerman	Summary report
Desk study: terminology	To provide a better understanding of the jargon used in user centred approaches and co-creation	Poppy Townsend	The desk study found there is lots of jargon, it can be very confusing. To simplify this, a decision was made to use the phrase 'user centred approaches' for this report to avoid confusing use of different terminology.
Desk study: policy barriers to contacting users	To provide a summary about who (users) each data centre can/can't contact due to the terms and conditions in their policies	Thomas Zwagerman	Summary report

3. Desk study: policy barriers to contacting users

Purpose: to provide a summary about who (users) each data centre can/can't contact due to the terms and conditions in their policies

Findings: Current issues identified included; differing policies across data centres allowing contact to be made or not, differing user metrics collected, no shared communication mechanism (i.e. mailing list, social media)

Outcome: a clearer understanding about the different barriers to contacting users based on each data centres current policies

Case studies

The purpose of the case studies was to empower individuals to trial and integrate collaborative and user centred approaches into their work. A summary of the case studies can be found below and in Table 3.

It was expected that individuals would share their learnings related to this trial with each other, and more broadly across the EDS (see knowledge sharing work in Table 4).

By embedding these approaches into existing work, it has encouraged our teams to begin to shift their mindsets and processes to be more user centred. It also allowed a low risk environment to trial using new approaches with a dedicated group of individuals to ask for support.

1. Data Centre Websites: assessing usability & navigation

Purpose: to assess the usability and navigation of five data centre websites, specifically identifying areas that could improve user experience, accessibility, and consistency.

Findings: a systematic assessment of the five data centre websites was undertaken using a heuristic evaluation method.

Output: a report was produced. It identified common issues such as; broken links, unclear navigation, search functionality problems. It also provided recommendations; simplifying content, improving search tools, and standardising design. The EDS now has clear areas that can be improved in future work.

2. BGS Website: redesigning to improve accessibility

Purpose: to address known issues with the BGS website such as; complex menus, unclear terminologies, and inconsistent data catalogues.

Findings: User research and iterative design process was undertaken with stakeholder input.

Output: the website structure was revamped to improve searchability and usability. New features were added such as; intuitive filters, improved metadata access, and responsive design.

3. BODC Data Submission: designing a new app

Purpose: streamline data submission processes to ensure consistent and timely submissions with complete metadata that can be captured once and reused throughout BODC's ingestion systems.

Findings: using Scrum methodologies for iterative improvements was vital after taking on user feedback.

Output: a central app was built which addresses multiple issues including poor metadata accompanying data, inconsistent and proprietary data files, reactive and time consuming archival process for data managers, automatic validation on key metadata, and providing a clear and easy way for data originators to submit their data.

4. Developer Portal: improving software collaboration

Purpose: to design a new service that centralises resources (tools, documents), provides templates and best practice, and integrates with other tools to improve workflows. The service must address the different needs of software engineers, DevOps, and data engineers.

Findings: collaborating on software and related workflows is a common challenge across the EDS. This case study found the use of 'Backstage' to be a useful mechanism for improving collaboration and encouraging good practice.

Output: a demonstration 'Developer Portal' service was designed with the needs of the users in mind (e.g. people in data engineers, software developers, DevOps) in mind. It could provide a centralised hub for software collaboration, ultimately leading to improved collaboration, transparency, and efficiency.

5. UKCEH DRI Futures: understanding attitudes, experiences and expectations

Purpose: to understand different attitudes, experiences and expectations of digital research infrastructure (DRI), and to develop DRI with enhanced functionality, and aligned to progressive data science principles such as 'FAIR' (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable).

Findings: participatory user research/co-creation undertaken to obtain user-centered insights into opportunities and challenges for the future of Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI), specifically for the needs of the UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology.

Output: vast amounts of data from surveys, workshops and interviews. Lessons learnt from delivering a large project solely focussed on gathering data from stakeholders.

6. CEDA climate data: communicating about complex services

Purpose: to explain how our different services can be used for different purposes and use cases, focussed on one particular climate dataset

Findings: our services are complex and need fairly detailed explanations about why/how each service could be used for particular use cases. We trialled creating a new style of help documentation, drafted by an external user (guided by internal staff) whose time was paid for by the project. It is a substantial piece of work that is yet to be published.

Output: draft blog style help documentation that uses a conversational narrative to guide the interested person to the relevant service that they need for their use case.

Table 3: summary of the case studies work

Case studies			
Title	Theme	People involved	Further information
Data Centre Websites: assessing usability & navigation	Improving existing services	Jesse Alexander Shwetha Raveendran	Summary report
BGS Website: redesigning to improve accessibility	Improving existing services	Shwetha Raveendran	Summary report
BODC Data Submission: designing a new app	Building new services	Monica Hanley Matt McCormack	Summary report
Developer Portal: improving software collaboration	Building new services	Dave Poulter	Summary report
UKCEH DRI Futures: understanding attitudes, experiences and expectations	Strategic planning	David Green Kelly Widdicks	Summary report
CEDA climate data: communicating about complex services	Improving existing services	Poppy Townsend David Hooper	Summary report

Knowledge sharing work

The purpose of the knowledge sharing work was to provide mechanisms for individuals to share their expertise and ask for advice. It also aimed to raise the profile and influence uptake of user centred approaches more generally across the EDS.

Three areas of work were covered, detailed below and in Table 4.

1. Co-creation toolkit for environmental data services

Purpose: to create a central location for sharing examples of best practice for user centred approaches specifically in the environmental science domain

Findings: an internal toolkit existed within one of the teams. It was adapted and turned into a public website, consisting of case study examples and a toolkit with helpful resources and templates for using user centred approaches. A review was undertaken of the toolkit from a non-UX perspective and changes were implemented.

Output: an online toolkit with case studies, templates, and guidance specifically for designing user centred environmental data services.

2. Webinar - Putting users first: how can we co-create environmental data services that address real needs

Purpose: to introduce, explore and promote the topic of creating user centred environmental data services.

Findings: a one hour webinar titled 'Putting users first: how can we co-create environmental data services that address real needs' was hosted in July 2024. Examples of good practice from experienced experts were shared. The new co-creation toolkit was introduced and feedback from participants was collected.

Output: feedback for future toolkit iteration and a list of 'critical friends' who were either willing to provide content for the toolkit or to review future iterations.

3. Forming an expert group

Purpose: to create a community of experts interested in creating user centred environmental data services

Findings: 15+ individuals from across the EDS and Digital Solutions project now meet regularly. The meetings are a way to share experiences, lessons learnt, and ask for advice.

Output: a network of experts who are passionate about embedding user centred approaches across the organisation.

Table 4: summary of the knowledge sharing work

Knowledge sharing			
Title	Purpose	People involved	Further information
Co-creation toolkit for environmental data services	To share good practice	Paulius Tvaranavicius Carl Watson Danny Lloyd	Summary report
Webinar on co-creation of environmental data services	To disseminate work internally	Paulius Tvaranavicius Carl Watson David Green Poppy Townsend	Summary report
Forming an expert group	To collaborate on project work and facilitate discussions	Poppy Townsend	Summary report

Challenge 2: Engagement with peers and conflicting priorities

Working with peers on cross-domain EDS work (rather than data centre specific work) is more common than it used to be. However, there is still a clear need to improve relationships between experts working in similar roles and managing similar services.

Issues related to this included; lack of visibility of expertise and who is doing what, complexity of what we do, legacy issues (e.g. siloed data/tools), lack of shared vision/mission/coordination makes it difficult to understand how work should be prioritised. Tackling these issues could result in staff feeling supported by a larger network of peers and improved understanding about how their individual work fits into the wider goals of the organisation.

The main area of work that tackled this challenge was the formation of the expert group - who were core to completing the work. At the end of the project, a retrospective discussion took place to understand what went well, what could have gone better, what surprised us and what we'd like to explore in the future.

Whilst it's clearly important to engage with our peers within the EDS, we also reached out to experts and organisations in the field of user centred approaches, either within environmental, data or digital domains. This is summarised in Table 5. We wanted to learn from their experiences and understand if the toolkit and/or a community of practice is something useful to explore in the future.

Table 5: a summary of organisations we contacted for an interview. The table indicates their research domain, where they are based, and the job role of individuals we reached out to. Formal interview notes have been included where possible.

Organisation	Organisation type	Domain	Country	Job role	Further information
Research Data Alliance	Community driven	Digital preservation and research data management	International	Research Scientist	Interview notes
NetDRIVE	Academic	Environmental science Interdisciplinary	UK	Project lead	Interview notes
Met Office	Executive agency	Environmental science	UK	Science Manager, International Climate Services User-experience lead, and Applied scientist	Interview notes Interview notes
University of Brighton	Academic	Economic, social, behavioural and human data science Computer science - AI, data science	UK	Principal Lecturer in Human Centred AI and Interaction	Interview notes
DAFNI DINI	Research infrastructure	Computer science - software, data science Engineering and physical sciences	UK	DAFNI Programme Lead, and Project Delivery Manager	Interview notes
Health Data UK	Government	Health	UK	User experience team	Interview notes

FAIR Data Accelerator	Academic	Digital preservation and research data management Economic, social, behavioural and human data science	UK	Project lead, social science researcher	Informal discussion so no notes available
IPCC Interactive Atlas	International community	Environmental science	International	Computer science PhD student	Informal discussion so no notes available
Sustainable Software Institute	Academic	Computer science - software	UK	Project Manager	Informal discussion so no notes available
Alan Turing institute	Independent charity	Computer science - AI, data science	UK	-	Informal discussion so no notes available
Catapult	Industry	Engineering and physical sciences	UK	-	Informal discussion so no notes available
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	Academic	Digital preservation and research data management	International	-	Ran out of time to organise interview
National Film and Sound Archive	Government	Digital preservation and research data management	International	-	No response to email
US geological survey	Government	Environmental research	International	-	Yes - limited time so no notes
NOAA	Government	Environmental research	International	-	No response to email
Surfers against sewage	Community driven / Independent charity	Environmental research, Health	UK	-	No response to email
Environment Agency	executive non-departmen	Environmental research	UK	-	No response to email

	tal public body				
Brunel University London	Academic	Economic, social, behavioural and human data science Environmental research	UK	-	No response to email
UK Government departments specialising in user centred approaches	Government	-	UK	-	Ran out of time to organise interview, email exchange instead
Sustainable DRI project	Academic	Computer science - AI, Data Science Environmental research	UK	-	Ran out of time to organise interview
ECMWF	Independent intergovernmental organisation	Environmental research Computer science - AI, Data Science Digital preservation and research data management	International	-	Ran out of time to organise interview
Earth Observation DataHub (EODH)	Research infrastructure, industry	Environmental research Computer science - AI, Data Science Digital preservation and research data management	UK	-	Ran out of time to organise interview

Challenge 3: Lack of time/resources

Staff are juggling lots of different priorities across the EDS, and may not necessarily be involved directly in this project. Until recent years, there has been no dedicated work focussed on user centred approaches. This was a common challenge across the individuals and organisations that we interviewed about this topic.

Issues related to this include; lack of clarity of roles and individual responsibilities for user centred approaches, unclear who is working in this area already, high workloads and conflicting priorities, skills gaps in teams, requires a mindset shift, historical focus has been on getting data in which is hard and time consuming so focus has been on internal developments.

The new resources created by this work (such as this report and the online toolkit) will help individuals to save time and guide them to increase user centred approaches within the organisation.

The key aspect this project funding allowed was the expert group to come together and tackle specific areas of work. We now have a clear group of individuals interested in championing and further embedding user centred approaches across the EDS. We have seen a shift in the awareness from the management teams and this work is beginning to become a higher priority in the EDS roadmap. This would not have been possible without the additional funding for the BOOST project.

Challenge 4: Difficult to engage with users/stakeholders

As our data becomes more open, we increasingly struggle to know who is using our data/services. We need to know who the users are, so we can convince them to engage with us.

There are many barriers in this area, including but not limited to; finding who our (anonymous) users are and how to reach them, difficult to get users interested in participating (data is seen as boring/dry), survey fatigue, needs to be iterative which is resource intensive, getting the right people engaged.

This final challenge area is arguably the most difficult, especially when a culture of user centred approaches has not yet been established maturely across the organisation.

As a first step, the desk study which reviewed the policy barriers for contacting users. This has provided us with a summary about who each data centre can or can't contact due to the terms and conditions in their policies. This work needs further development and dedicated time spent understanding what constraints could be lifted or reduced.

Due to the short funding timescale for this project, unfortunately we did not actually manage to engage with users of the EDS. This was a common challenge across the individuals and organisations that we interviewed about this topic.

What next?

Overall, there was a clear desire and need for people and projects dedicated to using user centred approaches. This was evident not just in environmental data services but across all domains and digital research infrastructures - as shown by the information synthesised in this report.

The expert group discussed what we would anticipate the future of this work to look like, based on our experience from this project and more broadly. Recommendations for future work are listed below and summarised in Table 6. The recommendations are framed in the context of three themes;

- people and communities,
- processes, governance and strategy,
- and information management.

Recommendations are predominantly framed in the context of the EDS, however, we believe they are broadly transferable across all research, digital and data domains.

1. People and communities

Recommendation 1a - build an international community of experts working in user centred environmental data domains. Activities should be community led but could include; show and tell webinars, bidding for funding collaboratively, career development support, etc.

Long term ambition - expand network to enable knowledge sharing across other research domains and digital research infrastructures involved in tackling environmental data challenges with user centred approaches.

Who can make this happen? How?

- Funders - create funding opportunity to enable this to happen
- Experts in environmental data - coordinate funding proposal, participate in community
- Experts in user centred approaches - participate in community
- Experts in community building, such as social scientists - set up, build and participate in community

Recommendation 1b - set up a consultant group of experts within the EDS for user centred approaches. Examples of tasks; give advice, help shape project proposals, be a sounding board, undertake user research, etc.

Long term ambition - these consultants are world leading experts involved in user centred approaches for international environmental data projects and initiatives.

Who can make this happen? How?

- Funders - create funding opportunity to enable this to happen

- EDS expert group (user centred approaches) - define and pitch idea to management team
- EDS management team - go/no go decision to allocate new or rearrange existing resources to support this new activity, ensure all new projects are user centred

Recommendation 1c - organise in person networking for people interested in user centred approaches to environmental data projects. For example, in 2025 this could be at the [NERC tech forum](#) and NERC digital gathering.

Long term ambition - collaborative user centred projects are the norm for environmental data in the UK.

Who can make this happen? How?

- Funders - explicitly include cross-discipline user centred projects in funding opportunities to encourage collaboration
- EDS management team - nominate someone to coordinate a networking opportunity at events that are popular to staff

2. Processes, governance and strategy

Recommendation 2a - explore creative ways to outsource user research work e.g. pitching user centred projects to MSc students studying user centred approaches.

Long term ambition - a diverse portfolio of user centred work is undertaken by a range of different staff, students, and external collaborators across the environmental data service.

Who can make this happen? How?

- EDS expert group (user centred approaches) - include in pitch to EDS management team for Recommendation 1b.

Recommendation 2b - pilot using holacracy software to define and visualise the diverse roles and expertise of staff across the EDS.

Long term ambition - anyone wanting to find an expert in environmental data in the UK can do this with ease. Individuals are empowered to work collaboratively and have well defined roles which are transparent to their peers.

Who can make this happen? How?

- EDS management team - allocate new or rearrange existing resources to support this new activity, ensure all new projects are user centred
- EDS expert group (user centred approaches) - use this expert group as a test case

Recommendation 2c - ensure this work is embedded in long term strategy and roadmap. For example, need to decide the governance around the toolkit and how it becomes an operational EDS service. This is difficult when projects are funded for a short period of time with no guarantee of future funds.

Long term ambition - the EDS is a leader in tackling environmental data challenges by using collaborative cross-discipline user centred approaches.

Who can make this happen? How?

- EDS management team - create a process to ensure all new projects are user centred and internal projects are created to embed user centred approaches in our core work
- Funders - explicitly include cross-discipline user centred projects in funding opportunities to encourage collaboration

Recommendation 2d - funders to promote trusted experts as collaborators in funding calls. If a funding call requires knowledge about user centred approaches and/or environmental data practices, it should require applications to indicate how they will make use of EDS expertise (such as the toolkit or consultants).

Long term ambition - EDS staff are funded team members within environmental project from their outset. The environmental science community actively include data experts within their research projects.

Who can make this happen? How?

- EDS management team - work with funders to understand how/if this could happen
- Funders - explicitly encourage funding proposals to include collaboration with EDS staff

3. Information management

Recommendation 3a - turn the toolkit into a fully supported operational EDS service.

Long term ambition - the toolkit is a popular resource used internationally by individuals designing and maintaining environmental data services.

Who can make this happen? How?

- Funders - create funding opportunity for operationalising pilot services (including legacy plan for if/when funding is not available)
- EDS management team - identify staff who have capacity to be responsible for the new service
- EDS expert group (user centred approaches) - create a launch plan to encourage new content and increased usage of the toolkit

- UKRI/DSIT - decide if domain specific good practice for user centred approaches is desirable by others working in digital research infrastructure roles. Decide if the toolkit should be expanded to cover all research domains.
- UKRI/DSIT - Decide if the toolkit should be expanded to contain other domain agnostic topics e.g. data sharing, training. Each topic could have domain specific guidance dependent on the culture and working practices of that domain.

Recommendation 3b - disseminate the findings from this work to priority stakeholders. For example, a poster is being presented at EGU in April.

Long term ambition - the EDS is a trusted international leader in tackling environmental data challenges by using collaborative cross-discipline user centred approaches.

Who can make this happen? How?

- EDS management team - relies on recommendation 1b
- EDS expert group (user centred approaches) - create a launch plan, with the EDS comms team, to advertise the new service. Use the EDS stakeholder map to prioritise dissemination.

Recommendation 3c - create an ongoing base of user research undertaken in environmental data domains. To reduce duplication of effort, a central repository for an ongoing base of user research knowledge should be created.

Long term ambition - a database of information that enables digital research infrastructures to adapt to future changes in environmental data use over the coming years.

Who can make this happen? How?

- EDS expert group (user centred approaches) - build on initial work to collate user research undertaken by the EDS and beyond
- Funders - facilitate knowledge sharing between projects who have undertaken user research
- UKRI/DSIT - embed user research findings into the reporting process (e.g. ResearchFish) and automate this information to be transferred into the centralised database.

Table 6: a summary of the projects recommendations, including the theme they fall under and who could make it happen

No.	Recommendation title	Theme	Who can make this happen?
1a	Build an international community of experts working in user centred environmental data domains	People and communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funders • Experts in environmental data, user centred approaches, community building
1b	Set up a consultant group of experts within the EDS for user centred approaches	People and communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funders • EDS expert group (user centred approaches) • EDS management team
1c	Organise in person networking for people interested in user centred approaches to environmental data projects.	People and communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funders • EDS management team
2a	Explore creative ways to outsource user research work	Processes, governance and strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EDS expert group (user centred approaches)
2b	Pilot using holacracy software to define and visualise the diverse roles and expertise of staff across the EDS	Processes, governance and strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EDS management team • EDS expert group (user centred approaches)
2c	Ensure this work is embedded in long term strategy and roadmap	Processes, governance and strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EDS management team • Funders
2d	Funders to promote trusted experts as collaborators in funding calls.	Processes, governance and strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EDS management team • Funders
3a	Turn the toolkit into a fully supported operational EDS service	Information management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funders • EDS management team • EDS expert group (user centred approaches) • UKRI/DSIT
3b	Disseminate the findings from this work to priority stakeholders	Information management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EDS management team • EDS expert group (user centred approaches)
3c	Create an ongoing base of user research undertaken in environmental data domains.	Information management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EDS expert group (user centred approaches) • Funders • UKRI/DSIT

Conclusion

How can user centred approaches be developed and implemented to enhance user experience on data analysis systems?

Overall, user centred approaches can be developed and implemented to enhance user experience on data analysis systems by focusing on practical and useful solutions for diverse communities. This approach ensures that the services we develop are relevant and beneficial to a wide range of users.

The funding we received allowed for greater integration and knowledge sharing across our work in the EDS and beyond, tackling siloed working, fostering collaboration and sharing good practice. It has enabled us to begin to shift our mindset towards being user centred in everything we do. Our journey towards becoming a truly user centred organisation is only just beginning. Our current guiding principles to embedding user centred approaches across our organisation are:

- **Listen and adapt:** we must understand diverse perspectives and redefine solutions to suit their needs
- **One size does not fit all:** use multiple customised methods (surveys, interviews, workshops) to get the information we need
- **Prioritise and facilitate:** we must carefully design and facilitate user centred approaches to ensure inclusivity and participation
- **Collaborate, share and disseminate:** it is an iterative process, we should share the highs and lows so others can benefit

By adhering to these principles, we hope to create data services that truly enhance user experience and meet the needs of the diverse users of environmental data.

With the current financial challenges in UK research funding, integration of user centred approaches for designing, maintaining and deprecating data analysis systems is essential. It will ensure we can prioritise our efforts, allowing us to focus on the highest impact areas of work. Looking ahead, we aim to enable others to adopt user centred approaches by providing guidance, support and expert leadership based on our experiences.

While the report authors work primarily in the environmental and data domains, we believe the findings and recommendations in this report are relevant to other research domains, in particular those working with digital research infrastructures. We would welcome the opportunity to discuss and collaborate with others interested in this area. Please contact poppy.townsend@stfc.ac.uk with any questions, comments or opportunities.

Supporting materials

Alexander, J., & Raveendran, S. (2025). Data Centre Websites: assessing usability & navigation. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115229>

Green, D., Widdicks, K., Lord, C., & Agyei, E. E. Y. F. (2025). UKCEH DRI Futures: understanding attitudes, experiences and expectations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15112891>

Hanley, M., & McCormack, M. (2025). BODC Data Submission: designing a new app. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15114777>

MacRae, M., Zwagerman, T., & Townsend, P. (2025). Interviews - Current state review. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15102198>

MacRae, M., & Townsend, P. (2025). Interview - DAFNI DINI project. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15101541>

MacRae, M., & Townsend, P. (2025). Interview - HealthUser experience team, Health Data UK. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15101406>

MacRae, M., & Townsend, P. (2025). Interview - Met Office International Climate Services. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15101485>

MacRae, M., & Townsend, P. (2025). Interview - Met Office User Experience. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15101469>

MacRae, M., & Townsend, P. (2025). Interview - NetDRIVE Project. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15101425>

MacRae, M., & Townsend, P. (2025). Interview - Research Data Alliance (RDA). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15101512>

MacRae, M., & Townsend, P. (2025). Interview - User-Centred Design (UCD) Lab at the University of Brighton. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15101297>

Poulter, D. (2025). Developer Portal: improving software collaboration. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15114741>

Raveendran, S., Tvaranavicius, P., & Watson, C. (2025). BGS Website Redesign: simplifying data access through intuitive design. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15114901>

Townsend, P., Tvaranavicius, P., Green, D., & Watson, C. (2025). Webinar - Putting users first: how can we co-create environmental data services that address real needs. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15102396>

Townsend, P., Tvaranavicius, P., Watson, C., Green, D., Alexander, J., Hanley, M., McCormack, M., Poulter, D., Raveendran, S., Zwagerman, T., Darroch, L., Heysham, N., Osunkoya, S., & Agyei, E. E. Y. F. (2025). Forming an expert group for user centred environmental data services. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15102557>

Townsend, P. (2025). Workshop outcomes and next steps for WP5 BOOST-EDS. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15130037>

Townsend, P., & Hooper, D. (2025). CEDA climate data: communicating about complex services. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15102708>

Tvaranavicius, P., & Lloyd, D. (2025). Co-Creation Toolkit for Environmental Services. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15102338>

Zwagerman, T. (2025). Policies for contacting our users - current barriers. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15132312>